

Business Profile Interview Script

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This document is a supplementary material of the paper “Analyzing the BizDev Interface in an Enterprise Context: A Case of Developers Acting in Business” by Caique G. Moreira, Breno B. N. de França, and Tayana U. Conte. Here, we provide the interview script applied to interviewees from the business area.

Warm Up:

- For how long have you been in the company?
- What is your current Job Position?
- How many people are on your team? What are their job positions?

Context information:

- What is your team responsible for? What are your main responsibilities?
 - For BizDev responsibilities: Who defined these responsibilities?
 - For BizDev responsibilities: Do you think you spend too much time fulfilling these responsibilities?
- Does your team have regular meetings? What are those meetings for? Who participates in them?
 - If people from the technology team participate: Do only tech leaders participate? Or is it also common for analysts to participate?

Requirements Handling:

- How are product requirements and new features defined? What teams participate in this process?
- Do you know of any projects or features that were proposed/defined by the technology team? Case positive:
 - How frequently does this happen? Does this happen for most features, or only for small features?
 - Were they successful? Why do you think so?
 - Were people from the business team involved on these projects? Were they aware of it?
 - What members of the tech team were involved? Were there analysts involved, or only tech leaders?

Communication on the BizDev interface:

- Do you usually need to communicate with people from the IT sector?
 - What teams do you communicate with?
 - What are the reasons for this communication? What is discussed?
 - How frequent is this communication?
 - How do you evaluate this communication? Do you think you

understand each other? Do some information tend to be lost in the process?

- Is communication efficient? Or is it slow?
- Do you think technology teams use too much technical jargon? If so, how do you think this affects communication?
- Do you think the communication with the IT sector could be improved?
 - Do you take any effort to improve this communication? Case positive, do you receive any help for this?
 - Have you perceived any effort taken by technology teams to improve this communication? Any effort taken by the company?

Relationship with development area:

- Have you noticed conflicts between business and technology areas?
 - What were the reasons for these conflicts?
 - What were the consequences?
 - Do you think these conflicts can still happen?
- Do you trust the decisions taken by technology teams? Why?
 - Do technology teams usually trust decisions taken by your team? Why?
- Have you perceived any type of action taken in order to improve the relationship between business and development areas? Case positive:
 - What was this action? Which team was responsible for it?
 - How do you compare this relationship before and after these actions?

Business and Tech Knowledge:

- How do you evaluate your technology knowledge? How do you evaluate your knowledge about the systems that support the company's products?
- Do people from the technology area usually take time to share technology knowledge with you and your team?
 - Case positive: How does this happen? How frequent is that? Who was behind the decision of sharing this knowledge?
- Do you or your team usually take time to share business knowledge with technology people?
 - Case positive: How does this happen? How frequent is that? Who was behind the decision of sharing this knowledge?

Reactive Points:

When interviewee describes any practice inserted on the BizDev Interface:

- Who defined this practice? What was the motivation behind it?
 - Do you think this practice matches a behavior described on the company's values?
- How frequent is this practice?
 - Do you think you spend too much time performing these practices?

When interviewee talks specifically about technology team performing practices directly linked to business (eg: definition/prioritization of requirements, performance analysis):

- Do analysts also take part in these activities? Or is it restricted to tech leadership?
- Is the business team receptive to these practices?

When the interviewee talks about the project created on PlayKids App in order to improve general process and communication:

- Do you think that project was necessary? Why?
- What was your participation in that project? How did it affect your work?
- Have you perceived significant changes brought by this project? What changed in terms of:
 - Communication between Business and Technology teams
 - Product quality
 - Overall performance and fulfillment of deadlines